

STUDIES IN CATALYTIC DEHYDRATION.

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Intramolecular catalytic dehydration has been shown to take place between ethers and ammonia in presence of thoria and alumina. The process has been extended to ether and aniline and very good yield of diethylaniline has been obtained.

Intramolecular dehydration has been attempted with numerous organic compounds and various catalysts. The present work is an attempt to prepare secondary amines and tertiary amines from ethers according to the following reactions.

Such reactions employing ethers do not appear to have been studied. Previous attempts to prepare primary amines have been made by Sabatier and Mailhe (*Compt. rend.*, 1909, 148, 900; 1911, 153, 160, 1204) from ammonia and alcohols using thoria as catalyst and by Roy (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 383) who obtained a good yield of a mixture of mono- and dimethylaniline from aniline and methyl alcohol using the same catalyst.

We have prepared various aliphatic secondary amines from the corresponding ethers and ammonia. Aromatic ethers like diphenyl oxide and anisole gave indications of the formation of amines but yielded appreciable quantities of unstable white needles which decomposed on exposure into corresponding ether and ammonia. With diethyl ether and aniline using alumina as a catalyst we have been able to get 86% yield of diethylaniline. From the experimental results it would appear that thoria in general is not a good catalyst for intramolecular dehydration between ethers and ammonia or amines.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Procedure.—Thoria was prepared from thorium nitrate by heating to drive off nitrous fumes. Aluminium oxide was prepared from alum by

precipitating aluminium hydroxide by ammonia, washing the precipitate free from sulphate and ammonia, and igniting it at 150° for several hours. For the preparation of aliphatic amines, ammonia gas, generated by allowing liquor ammonia to drop on to solid sodium hydroxide (stick) and dried by passage through towers containing dry quick lime, soda lime and anhydrous potassium carbonate, was passed through anhydrous ether and the mixed vapour was led over thoria or alumina in a combustion tube heated at the requisite temperature in a combustion furnace. The receiver, connected by an adapter with the combustion tube, was fitted with a condenser cooled by circulation of iced water. For the preparation of diethylaniline, the vapour of anhydrous ether was passed through dry aniline kept near its boiling point and the mixed vapour was treated as above.

Experiments with Aliphatic Ethers and Ammonia.

Higher ethers were prepared by the method of Senderens (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 1015). The presence of the respective secondary amines was proved by the preparation of picrates and hydrochlorides. The reaction products were dried over quick lime and treated with mercuric oxide to remove traces of ammonia, filtered and analysed. A definite amount of the clear liquid was treated with acetic anhydride and the excess was titrated with *N/10*-baryta solution. The following results were obtained.

<i>Diethyl ether.</i>		
Catalyst.	Temperature of reaction.	Yield of diethylamine.
Thoria	275-285°	1.693%
"	350°	1.263
"	400°	0.3502
"	425°	0.6219
Alumina	200°	5.682
"	250°	6.183
"	300°	3.996
<i>n-Propyl ether.</i>		
Catalyst.	Temperature of reaction.	Yield of dipropylamine.
Thoria	250°	3.747%
"	300°	8.262
"	350°	3.788
Alumina	250°	1.574
"	300°	2.424

n-Butyl ether

Catalyst.	Temperature of reaction.	Yield of dibutylamine.
Thoria	250°	0.4996%
"	300°	1.057
"	350°	0.861
Alumina	250°	2.1
"	300°	0.34

n-Amyl ether.

Catalyst.	Temperature of reaction.	Yield of diamylamine.
Thoria	250°	3.322%
"	300°	3.633
"	350°	3.515
Alumina	270°	3.006

Diethyl ether and Aniline.

The reaction product was dehydrated over quick lime and weighed. A portion was diazotised and titrated against standardised R-salt; another portion was acetylated and excess of acetic anhydride was titrated back with baryta (*cf. Roy, loc. cit.*). In this way the percentages of aniline, monoethylaniline and diethylaniline were determined. The following are results with alumina.

Temperature of reaction.	Weight of aniline.	Weight of reaction product.	Aniline.	Mono-ethylaniline.	Diethylaniline.
370-375°	102 g.	96 g.	12%	14%	74%
395-400°	81.6	82	12	17	71
415°	91.8	81	10	25	65

It would appear from the foregoing results that although the yield of tertiary amine was high, there was some decomposition of the product which increased with the rise of temperature.